

D3.4 – Prototype system description and test results

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D3.4 Prototype system description and test results

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Abstract

This document describes the various prototype components of the BIMprove system. These mainly consist of the data acquisition systems (drones, robots), the analysis part and the backend. Test results are presented here in a very individualized way in the subcomponents (satellites). The interaction of these subcomponents is part of further overall tests at the pilot construction sites. Numerous components have already been described in other deliverables; reference is made to them here accordingly.

Keywords

Prototype, data processing, BIM, testing, construction processes

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AR	Augmented Reality
MR	Mixed Reality
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (here: drone)
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle (here: also called <i>ground robots</i>)
CS	Coordinate System
TP	Test Person
VR	Virtual Reality
PC	Point Cloud
UI	User Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
MR	Mixed Reality
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (here: drone)
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle (here: also called <i>ground robots</i>)

BIMprove project

In the past 20 years, productivity in the European construction industry has increased by 1% annually only, which is at the lower end compared to other industrial sectors. Consequently, the sector has to step up its digitization efforts significantly, on the one hand to increase its competitiveness and on the other hand to get rid of its image as dirty, dangerous and physical demanding working environment. Construction industry clearly needs to progress beyond Building Information Modelling when it comes to digitizing their processes in such a way that all stakeholders involved in the construction process can be involved.

The true potential of comprehensive digitization in construction can only be exploited if the current status of the construction work is digitally integrated in a common workflow. A Digital Twin provides construction companies with real-time data on the development of their assets, devices and products during creation and also enables predictions on workforce, material and costs.

BIMprove facilitates such a comprehensive end-to-end digital thread using autonomous tracking systems to continuously identify deviations and update the Digital Twin accordingly. In addition, locations of construction site personnel are tracked anonymously, so that **BIMprove** system services are able to optimize the allocation of resources, the flow of people and the safety of the employees. Information will be easily accessible for all user groups by providing personalized interfaces, such as wearable devices for alerts or VR visualizations for site managers. **BIMprove** is a cloud-based service-oriented system that has a multi-layered structure and enables extensions to be added at any time.

The main goals of **BIMprove** are a significant reduction in costs, better use of resources and fewer accidents on construction sites. By providing a complete digital workflow, BIMprove will help to sustainably improve the productivity and image of the European construction industry.

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1. Data Acquisition System

1.1. Ground based DA-Systems

The selected ground robot for the data acquisition is the Summit XL. It has skid-steering kinematics based on 4 high power motor-wheels. Each wheel integrates a hub brushless motor with gearbox and encoder that provides odometry data to the system. The platform has a strong mechanical structure allowing it to carry different sensors with a good stability.

Figure 1 Summit-XL with RS-Lidar 16, Flir Ax8 and BLK 360

The main sensor is the RS-Lidar 16, a 3D laser composed of 16 horizontal beams that provides depth information. It allows the ground robot to move safely avoiding and stopping before impacting with an object or a person. This laser is used to create a map for localization and autonomous navigation.

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To detect temperature anomalies in the working site, it has mounted a Flir Ax8. This thermal camera can provide thermal and RGB images. The ground robot can access these images thanks to the ROS node that works as a bridge to connect the camera with the robotics system. Moreover, this camera has a web page to set up alerts when the temperature is higher than a threshold level.

For the capture of the pointclouds it is used the BLK360. It is a high precision imaging laser scanner that can merge depth information with images to add colour to the pointcloud. It can generate a pointcloud of an entire floor by merging smaller pointclouds from different positions. Each of these smaller steps takes a default time of 2:50 minutes to be generated, this process can take more or less time depending on the quality of the pointcloud.

The data capturing process for the pointcloud data can be done in 2 different ways:

1. Using a tablet connected to the BLK360 laser.
2. Connecting the BLK360 laser directly to the ground robot.

These methods are more convenient depending on the needs. On one hand, if the data capturing is done with the tablet, the operator has immediate control on the results. Having the capabilities of selecting different qualities of the pointcloud and reviewing the result of one spot before moving to the next one, thanks to this the operator can repeat the scanning if there are moving objects or workers around and the resulting pointcloud is not satisfactory.

On the other hand, if the BLK360 is being used through the ground robot, the process can be done autonomously generating a mission on the robot HMI. This can be useful for generating a routine of capturing data every day at times that there is no work being done.

As an alternative to the BLK360, the BLK ARC was also tested. This is an autonomous laser scanning module for robotic integrations. From the robotic system the BLK360 can be used to start/stop a scan and to download the pointclouds. The BLK ARC can also send live information from the pointcloud and its own odometry for localization and navigation.

1.1.1. Fyrstikkbakken, Oslo, Norway

At Fyrstikkbakken the BLK 360 and the BLK ARC were compared, scanning the basement and the 2nd floor from building D.

Figure 2 Resulting pointcloud from the basement taken with BLK ARC

Figure 3 Resulting pointcloud from the basement taken with BLK 360

Figure 4 Details of the BLK ARC pointcloud

Figure 5 Details of the BLK 360 pointcloud

It can be observed that with the BLK 360 the pointcloud has more details but it is more time consuming and sometimes the merging between the small pointclouds is difficult to make with an optimal alignment. Meanwhile the BLK ARC creates the complete pointcloud on the go, but with less quality and details.

1.1.2. Lausanne, Switzerland

At Lausanne we were able to capture some thermal data from melting work, and to scan some apartments to get a pointcloud, also while this scanning was done, the thermal camera and the odometry were recorded.

Figure 6 Worker preparing for melting works

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Figure 7 Worker doing melting works

Figure 8 Odometry data and thermal image from the robot

Figure 9 Resulting pointcloud from the apartments

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Figure 10 Details of the pointcloud

Figure 11 Robot odometry superposed on the top view of the pointcloud

1.2. Airborne DA-Systems

1.2.1. Drone Systems

One main focus was the development of a drone system capable for indoor flights (GPS denied areas). This development can also be used outside but for outdoor data acquisition (with GPS available) typically commercial drones (DJI) were used. The great advantage of the in-house development is that it can be much better integrated into the overall BIMprove system process: Request for data - path planning - actual mission - data processing - feeding back into the backend. This is only possible to a limited extent - or not at all - with commercial systems.

1.2.1.1 Commercial Drone System

The drone system that has been in the data capture process for outside scan so far in the project is the DJI Mavic 2 pro, a commercial drone which can be found easily in the market. This drone is very reliable for taking photos outside since this is the purpose the drone was developed for. Meaning that photos taken from the drone are decent and quite powerful for photogrammetry required in BIMprove project. Moreover, the drone has got many third-party applications for easing taking photos including mission planning and automatic photo taking function, etc.

- Third-Party Mission Planning and Automatic Photo Taking Software

These are two third-party software that get tested during the project. They both deliver relatively the same results regarding path planning and photos taking function. Most of the time, grid planning (Top-view) and manual mission planning mode (Side-view) will be used for data capturing with automatic photo taking function.

Table 1 Overview of available software solutions

No.	Description	Picture
1	PIX4DCapture Software Available in both Android and iOS used for mission planning and taking aerial photos for photogrammetry	<p>PIX4DCapture</p>

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2	Drone Harmony, another mission planning and aerial photos taking software	<p data-bbox="1023 488 1233 521">Drone Harmony</p>
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1.2.1.2 Custom Drone System

The drone consists of numerous individually developed components. This is the third generation of a UAV, the development of which started before the BIMprove project and has been extended here by some functionalities.

The focus on in-house development has the advantage that new needs and ideas can be addressed very flexibly within the project (for example, an IR camera was not planned at the start of the project) and the system provides a powerful flight platform that can also be used and expanded in future projects.

Both the mechanical hardware, the electronic hardware, the mechanical components and the various embedded software components are in our hands. Only the motors (quadcopter and gimbal) and the motor controllers for the thrust motors are commercial systems. However, since these are highly standardized, alternatives can also be used there. The following figure shows the drone's main components.

Figure 12 Details of custom quadcopter

Figure 13 Top-view of custom quadcopter

1.2.1.2.1 Mechanical Setup

The mechanical setup is kept simple, consisting of 4 carbon tubes with integrated motor controllers. The central part consists of CNC machined 3mm carbon parts that can be customized to meet new needs (e.g. a different payload). Currently motors are equipped with 11" carbon propellers, these could be reduced to 9.5" propellers resulting in a smaller overall size, but with fewer reserves for lifting additional equipment. The total weight is currently 1.61 kg, including the RGB camera, gimbal etc. The battery pack consists of 2x Li-Ion batteries 4S, 3000mAh each. They are connected to a custom-made battery management and charging electronics. This allows the drone to recharge after landing on the charging station.

1.2.1.2.2 Flight Controller Software

The flight controller software runs on a H7-Arm processor from [Mateksys](#). It is a C++ embedded firmware developed with the ST-MBed OS6 operating system. The core of the drone software consists of approximately 40 different C++ classes. In addition, external libraries (e.g. Eigen-library for matrix-vector manipulation) and drivers are used. The free [Mbed Studio](#) is used as an IDE. This firmware is connected to many external sensors (IMU, IntelRealsense, Barometer, GPS, ...) and also a remote control. It is developed in a way, that it allows the drone to fly either with the remote control or fully autonomously. It does not necessarily need a data-connection to the ground (apart from the standard 2.4GHz remote control) or other external sensors.

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1.2.1.2.3 Electronic Components

Table 2 the main electronic components of custom quadcopter

Mateksys Flight controller directly soldered on a custom-made adapter board.

The adapter board connects to external sensors (some connectors are still unused and are still available for other purposes), to the motor controllers and the gimbal. It also carries a ESP32-WIFI module for a direct datalink from the FC to the ground and an SD-card for an on-board datalogging.

Two motor drivers for the gimbal electronics. The software of the motor hardware (already developed before) was adapted to special needs for the two gimbal motors.

Gimbal rotational sensor with magnetic off-axis sensor. The 15pin connector carries motor wires and SPI-connection for up to 3 motors.

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Charging electronics for 2 Li-Ion standard batteries. After landing the landing base/charging station can connect two pins (ground and 18V seen on top left) to it, such that batteries are recharged.

1.2.1.2.4 Drone Computer Software

A second computational unit is mounted on the drone: it is a Raspberry Pi4 8GB, which has different purposes: it is a wireless data connection node to the ground station, is connected to the RGB or IR camera and does the superordinate path planning based on requested mission. It is connected via a UART connection to the flight controller. The data connection is described in more detail in D2.3.

The path planning is based on requested mission (consisting of waypoints) and BIM-data converted to an octomap such that a feasible path is found based on a modified A* algorithm in 3 dimensions. A more detailed description and test results of this are currently being prepared for publication.

1.2.1.2.5 Drone Cockpit

Apart from the UAV (Drone) development, the ground station software or the application that sits in between the drone and the backend or the drone and a photogrammetry program, needs to be developed as well in order to facilitate the workflow, both in converting images to pointclouds and data transfer between backend and the drone.

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Figure 14 Overall Drone Cockpit

In overall, the drone cockpit software has 4 main functionalities, which are described in the table below. The testing results are quite reliable so far regarding all communication, file transfer and all functionalities.

Table 3 Cockpit software functionalities

Nr.	Functionality	Description	Flow	Picture
1	Drone Control	This function deals with controlling the drone e.g., displaying drone information, waypoint information handling, some simple drone controls to let the drone be controlled easier through GUI.	Backend <=> Drone Cockpit <=> Drone	 Drone Control Page
2	Photogrammetry Facilitating	This function is the semi-automated process described in (D3.2 Functional samples description and test	Drone <=> Drone Cockpit <=> PIX4D	

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		results) under the topic of “User Interaction and Automation of Processes” to run PIX4D automatically.		PIX4D Execution Page
3	Data Transfer	In this function, the drone cockpit should be able to communicate both backend and the drone. Meaning that both communication and file transfer can be done back and forth from/to the drone cockpit regarding drone images, thermal images, Octomap file, pointclouds, etc.	Drone <=> Drone Cockpit <=> Backend PIX4D <=> Drone Cockpit <=> Backend	<p>Backend Data Transfer</p>
4	Auxiliary Functions	Auxiliary functions are a group of functions that ease the workflow, for example, converting bounding box JSON file to Octomap file for the drone through Python, embedding positional data into EXIF metadata of the drone images, and seeking drone-related issue in issue boards on the backend, etc.	Backend <=> Drone Cockpit <=> Drone	<p>Issue Board</p>

With all these functions, the test for the prototype system is eased to facilitate the workflow.

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1.2.1.2.6 PIX4D

The functionality and results are published already in: [D3.2 Functional samples description and test results](#).

1.2.1.2.7 Data Connections

A detailed description of the data connections can be found in: D2.7 User interface software and interface description, which can be downloaded from the [Zenodo repository](#).

1.3. Tests and test results

1.3.1. Drone Testing

The following table gives a very brief overview of the tests with the different drones. In general the number of lift-off/landings and flight times can only be approximated based on data logs captured on the flight controller.

Table 4 Overview of tested drones

	<p>Custom made 2nd Gen (2 specimen):</p> <p>500 starts, approx. 44h flight time in total</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• development of controller software• data capture (RGB) photogrammetry in 2 labs at ZHAW• IR image data capture (lab)• outdoor flights for sensor tests, system identification
	<p>Custom made 3rd Gen (2 specimen):</p> <p>80 starts, approx. 4h flight time</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• development of controller software• outdoor IR data capture

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	<p>DJI Mavic 2 Pro</p> <p>approx. 100 starts, 20h flight time</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • system testing • outdoor data capture (photogrammetry), see table 5 for more details
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1.3.2. Data Capture and Processing

Table 5 PIX4D (Photogrammetry) results

Nr.	Description	Picture
1	<p>VIAS site, Madrid, Spain</p> <p>During the construction phase, the photos taken from the site were good for photogrammetry as seen in the model because of non-homogeneous texture surfaces of the building. Thus, generating pointclouds out of this data was easy and straightforward.</p> <p>Later when the building is complete, the result is extremely bad due to reflecting surfaces from glass on the surface of the building, which is unacceptable for photogrammetry. Generating model or pointclouds is not possible.</p>	<p>Complete Phase Result</p>
2	<p>Fyrstikkbakken, Oslo, Norway</p> <p>The results from Fyrstikkbakken was very nice thanks to the weather (lighting condition, which was cloudy but still very much bright.) that was perfect for photogrammetry, and an appropriate manual mission planning from the third-party application. Therefore, generating</p>	<p>Whole Construction Area Result</p>

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	<p>models were done straightforward and the results were decent.</p>	<p>Top of Building D Result</p>
3	<p>Weingarten, Germany</p> <p>As the result can be seen, the whole building was captured nicely, even though, the post processing needed some manual calibrations.</p>	<p>Area Captured Result</p>

2. Analytics

2.1. pyBIMprove

Both revision control and deviation detection are described and documented in: [D3.1 - Technology Demonstrations](#)

In Table 6 the new functionalities are listed.

Table 6 Overview of added functionalities displaying geometric difference and deviation classification

Functionality	Description	Details
Heat colouring	For showing geometric deviation between scan and BIM	
Deviation classification	Describing what deviation possibly exists between scan and each element in BIM	<p>Localisation deviation: Deviation of element according to global localisation</p> <p>Volumetric deviation: Deviation of extent between filtered point cloud and extent of BIM element:</p> <p>Internal points deviation: Deviation of rejected points from point cloud “inside” BIM element (high count indicates geometric deviation), Example from Fyrstikkbakken below, green is accepted points to BIM element (grey object image1), red is rejected points, Image 2 shows large red area, on left hand side, inside BIM element</p>

2.2. ROVAS – Risk Object Visual Analysis System

Deep learning and computer vision-based detection of safety and risk issues consists of an image analysis, ROVAS – Risk Object Visual Analysis System, engine and transformation of the results into BCF issues. Whenever safety risk factors (i.e. safety nets, safety barriers, or untidy places) are detected from construction site photographs or videos, the results are subsequently submitted to the Bimsync for further handling. These functionalities are explained in more detail in BIMprove deliverables [2.4](#) and [2.5](#). The evaluation of the image analysis results is elaborated in deliverable [3.3](#). Although the computer vision model is subsequently updated with more training data, the evaluation results are at the same levels although the model is currently capable to detect larger variation of safety barriers.

2.3. Feedback to Digital Twin (DT)

The basic functionality of ROVAS - the detection of essential safety elements - has been described above. However, in order to increase safety on the construction site, it is especially important when safety devices are missing where they are actually needed and intended.

This functionality was also developed and is a good example of how the real construction site and its digital twin interact with each other and exchange information - thus understanding the DT as a dynamic system.

Figure 15 The cycle of data capturing, data analysis and update of the Digital Twin

This is shown in the Figure 15. The starting point is a geometry model and the definition of safety elements (here: barriers). Data acquisition with drones is actually intended for geometry surveying. However, the data can also be processed with the ROVA system and additionally with additional information (where and at what angle was the image taken). Together with the detection of e.g. barriers, this can now be compared with the safety model and checked whether these facilities are present where required. If not, a BCF-issue can be generated and transmitted to the responsible person.

The development of these has progressed to the point where data collection and storage is largely automated. For the processing of the data, a desktop solution has been implemented so far, the implementation on the backend is still pending. Also still missing is the automatic generation of the BCF-issue.

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Figure 16 Desktop version of the safety detection system

2.4. Tests and test results: Detecting Safety Elements

The functionality of ROVAS together with the connection to the safety model was prototypically tested on two construction sites. The tests were limited with the focus on safety barriers.

Table 7 Summary of safety barrier detections

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- At VIAS only small regions were defined as a safety model (top left).
- 80 drone photos were taken and fed to the ROVASystem (top right).
- Results from ROVAS were processed together with 6DOF information of each photo and the safety model. Missing barriers were marked, a “missing barrier” model created from it and visualized in the model viewer (Bimsync).

Safety barriers detection at Fyrstikkbakken Oslo

- At Fyrstikkbakken again only a small region was considered with the system
- approx. 200 photos were taken at that region and processed by ROVAS
- The ROVAS detects barriers with a high reliability. In a central part, a staircase is not detected as a barrier, resulting in a “missing barrier” issue. Also missing barriers on the far right were not detected, since no photos have been taken there.

3. User Interfaces

3.1. BIM@Construction: Mixed Reality version

The functional prototype of BIM@Construction has been introduced in [D1.3](#). BIM@Construction has two versions (HoloLens 2 and tablet). Only HoloLens 2 mixed reality version was tested.

Figure 17 Left: Compare as-design to as-built in the 1st person mode. Right: Hand menu

3.1.1. User Tests

The functional tests were done during user tests. There were five (5) test subject in the user test. System has two modes, the first and the third-person view. In the first-person view, the user experiences the building as if inside the building, either by using MR. In the third-person view, the user sees the building as an outside viewer. User had a scenario to execute which includes (1) HoloLens 2 training, (2) overview of general features via video, and (3) testing the system by performing test tasks.

Table 8 Functional testing procedure

Phase	Item description	Goal / Research question	Method
Introduction	Introduction to test, test goals, and procedure		
HoloLens 2 training	HoloLens 2 training with Microsoft Tips software	Get user familiar with MR devices and its interaction metaphor	
BIM@Construction introduction	Showing video of the main features of the BIM@Construction MR tool	Get user familiar with BIM@Construction MR tool	
Actual test tasks	Compare as-design to as-built in the 1st person mode.	usability of interaction techniques	think-aloud (qualitative)

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	<p>From UI select various layers (e.g. ventilation) to compare to actual structure</p> <p>Using tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using measurement tool to measure door width • Add symbol in 3D space • Floor plan • Checking 2D floor plan • 3rd person view of the BIM model • Select various BIM layers and visually check them in 3D model. Rotate and zoom the model. 		
break			
Post-Questionnaire	System Usability Scale (SUS)	quick quantitative usability questionnaire for evaluating system usability	questionnaire (quantitative)
Interview part	<p>For both devices, but focus on more advanced HoloLens 2 application</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Please use 2-3 words (adjectives) to describe your experience with the AR system. Choose the words based on your immediate impression. • Please explain why you chose these words / adjectives. 	User experience and usability of the system, system usefulness, user needs and ideas.	semi-structured interview (qualitative)

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	<p>Dedicated question for Menus and interaction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• 3rd person mode• 1st person mode• floor plan / 2d map• Hololens 2 tools, like measuring tool, signs• Comfort of use• Future improvements and missing features		
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3.1.2. Results and Conclusions

All users were able to execute all required evaluation steps with HoloLens 2. All the functions and modes were working properly and gave feed to user via GUI without noticeable delay. One test user felt minor simulator sickness symptoms while using HoloLens 2.

Overall, test users were satisfied or even impressed about the HoloLens 2 solution. Most of the users found out that main benefit of the system is bringing BIM model on site and it will make easier to compare as-design to as-built.

More detailed results of the user test will be reported in the latest version of [D1.3](#).

3.2. BIM@SiteOffice multi-user VR user tests

These evaluations have been published ([open-access](#)) and reported in Aust, M; Otto, M.; Schippert, J., Frohnmayr, J.; Helin, K.; Liinasuo, M; Kuula, T.; Evaluation of BIMprove XR User Interfaces; In: Proceedings of the EuroXR Conference; Helin, K.; Reyes-Lecuona, A; Runde, C. (eds.), 2022). The BIM@SiteOffice multi-user-VR-system (aka. XR Viewer) has been described in Deliverables [D1.3](#), [D2.8](#) and [D2.7](#), among others.

Two “in-field” usability tests were conducted to evaluate the XR Viewer, one in the construction site office of the PUC in Madrid, and one in the site office of the PUC in Lausanne. Test persons included site managers, BIM managers, safety managers, and foremen. The testing procedure was the same for both tests and followed a similar structure as the BIM@Construction tests described above:

It was divided into four phases: Introduction, tasks, questionnaires, and interview. The tasks were divided into two sessions: a single-user and a two-user session. During both sessions participants were asked to think-aloud. Tasks in the single-user session included learning the interaction techniques for navigation (travel), using the hand-UI, using the Issue-Manipulation-Mode with which

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annotations can be created and shared, and closely inspecting a specific BIM model. A short questionnaire on cybersickness and sense of presence was deployed after the single-user session, followed by a short interview. Tasks in the two-user session were to apply the techniques learned in the first session and communicate with the other participant about the BIM models, find issues and try to solve them. These were BIM models of “their” building, together with scanned point clouds of the construction. Afterwards, two more questionnaires were used: the SUS and a short one on group presence and cybersickness. A final interview followed.

3.2.1. Results

The overall feedback to the XR Viewer was positive. Some interaction techniques were difficult to remember for the participants and some took too long to execute, which resulted in functionality not being used. Navigation seems to lack functionality – participants wished for more features, there.

The average SUS score was 79/100 (lowest 65, highest 95). Sickness was not an issue (all scores 2 or below on a 1 to 5 likert scale, avg. 1.4).

More detailed results of the user tests will be reported in the latest version of [D1.3](#).

4. The Backend

The Backend in BIMprove provides a set of functionalities it to the system:

1. It acts as an application server, and hosts software like pyBIMprove (see section 2.1).
2. It acts like a file server, and can host and serve for example images captured
3. It is connected with the model server, point cloud server and BCF server (Bimsync). When point clouds are uploaded, BIM objects indicated in BCF can be automatically compared with point cloud data and results will be added to BCF issues assigned to the correct roles.
4. It is a web server that provides the web GUI for BIMprove and exposes several of the functions in BIMprove. Special GUIs are added to indicated device/worker positions (privacy taken into account), mission planning for drones/robots, and other functions.
5. It supports uploading a schedule (currently MS project format only), showing this as a Gantt chart in a web GUI, and connection that with the BIM objects.
6. It is also a API server that uses the OpenAPI standard / “Swagger” and allows trying endpoints in a web GUI
7. It can be seen as a running version of the digital twin of the construction projects

4.1. Tests and test results

Several of the functions above are non-visual, so in those cases screenshots would not be possible. But for many direct or closely related screenshots are provided below. The BIMprove system will at the projects end be a prototype, and is still under development/integration, so many functions will still be improved within the project.

4.1.1.1 App server

See pyBIMprove results above.

4.1.1.2 File server:

Supported

4.1.1.3 Connection with the model/point cloud/BCF server

This is working and task scheduling is done via the python library “Huey”.

4.1.1.4 Main web application

This is established and available for any modern web browser on the internet (<https://cloud.bimprove-h2020.eu/>). There is still some work in progress, but support many of the functionalities planned. It also has a simple user access control layer (ACL).

D3.4 Prototype system description and test results

Figure 18 Main web application welcome page

4.1.1.5 Schedule

This is work in progress, but uploading schedules, visualizing them in the web application, and linking between tasks and BIM objects works. Currently only supports MPP files.

Figure 19 Schedule and BIM model visualized

D3.4 Prototype system description and test results

4.1.1.6 API server

Swagger doc is generated from the code, the more annotation the code includes, the richer the docs become.

← → ↻ 🔒 Ikke sikker | <https://cloud.bimprove-h2020.eu/docs>

Bimprove Backend 1.0.0 OAS3

/openapi.json

Backend for Bimprove! Check us out: [HERE](#)

[Authorize](#)

HTML Pages

Pages to access in your browser.

- GET /index.html Show Bimprove home page
- GET /login.html Show Bimprove login page
- GET /project/{project_guid}/issueboard/{issueboard_guid} Show BCF issue board in browser
- GET /project/{project_guid}/issueboard/{issueboard_guid}/topics/{topic_guid} Show BCF issue in browser
- GET /project/{project_guid} Show Bimprove project page
- GET /project/{project_guid}/model/{model_guid} Show Bimprove model page
- GET /project/{project_guid}/models/{model_guid} Show Bimprove model page
- GET /project/{project_id}/library/{library_id}/upload.html Upload file to library through web interface
- POST /project/{project_id}/library/{library_id}/upload.html Upload file to library through web interface, get html response

Figure 20 API server documentation

← → ↻ 🔒 Ikke sikker | https://cloud.bimprove-h2020.eu/redoc#tag/API-Endpoints/operation/post_ids_to_guids_project__project_id_ids_to_guids_post

Translate object ids to guides

Translate ids from 3D-viewer to object-guids usable in bimsync. Post a list of ids to translate.

AUTHORIZATIONS: > OAuth2PasswordBearer

PATH PARAMETERS

- project_id (required) string (Project id)

REQUEST BODY SCHEMA: application/json

```
Array [
  string
]
```

Responses

- > 200 Successful Response
- > 422 Validation Error

Get issue boards from project

Get all issue boards from project

AUTHORIZATIONS: > OAuth2PasswordBearer

PATH PARAMETERS

- project_id (required) string (Project id) [a-fA-F0-9]{32}

Request samples

Payload

Content type: application/json

```
[ ]
```

Response samples

- 200 422
- Content type: application/json

```
null
```

Figure 21 Further example on documentation

D3.4 Prototype system description and test results

4.1.1.7 Digital twin

This is non-visual but can be illustrated with showing a set of IFC models and a point cloud from the pilot project “Fyrstikkbakken” (from AF Gruppen).

Figure 22 Illustration of how Digital Twin can be interpreted

The above are the results of tests with the Backend at the time of writing. Things are still in quick progress. Further tests will be done, next main set is planned to be related to the Pilot Use-Case in Oslo (February or March 2023).